

Project acronym: CS3MESH4EOSC

Deliverable D5.1: Communication and stakeholder engagement plan

Contractual delivery date	30-09-2020
Actual delivery date	30-09-2020
Grant Agreement no.	863353
Work Package	WP5
Nature of Deliverable	R (Report)
Dissemination Level	PU (Public)
Lead Partner	Trust-IT Services
Document ID	CS3MESH4EOSC-20-005
Authors	Francesca Spagnoli, Sara Pittonet, Stephanie Parker, Rita Meneses, Silvana Muscella, Lorenzo Calamai (Trust-IT)

Disclaimer:

The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863353

Abstract

Deliverable 5.1 provides information about the marketing and stakeholder engagement plan for the CS3MESH4EOSC project as part of the work to be developed under WP5, and specifically under Task 5.4 Communications. The document includes both a communication and a stakeholder engagement strategy and related KPIs.

Executive summary

This communication, marketing and stakeholder engagement strategy details the methods to be used to present Science Mesh to the key target audience of the CS3MESH4EOSC project, composed of researchers, industry, developers, policy makers, and citizens.

The strategy is divided into 3 main project phases. While the first phase is mainly devoted to developing and testing the Science Mesh as the main asset of CS3MESH4EOSC, the second stage revolves around inviting early adopters from both academia and the industrial sector. The third phase is focused on enlarging the Science Mesh community as a whole for its full deployment into the market.

Chapter 3 contains the draft communication and stakeholder engagement plan which focuses on 5 main implementation steps: *Preliminary Communication & Marketing Strategy, second version of the Communication & Marketing Strategy, Stakeholder engagement for adoption of Science Mesh, Community Engagement, and Impact & Sustainability.*

The deliverable also provides an overview of the new version of the project website that will be made public at the end of September 2020, and identifies all the channels to be used and the key activities to be deployed to ensure sound and effective communications.

A specific engagement strategy is identified for each target audience and there is a detailed recruitment plan for each stakeholder, which includes a set of KPIs to track the work in progress. The same KPI-driven approach is applied in the marketing and communication plan, with results achieved being analysed both monthly via a “Flash Report”, and by way of automated software that visualises and tracks the communication and dissemination results.

Table of Contents

Executive summary	2
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Purpose	5
1.2 Structure of the document.....	5
1.3 CS3MESH4EOSC main assets.....	5
2 Marketing and communication strategy	7
2.1 CS3MESH4EOSC communication goals and objectives	8
2.2 Identifying the target audiences	8
2.3 Benefits and key messages to stakeholders	9
2.4 Stakeholder engagement strategy and KPIs	11
3 CS3MESH4EOSC Communication & Marketing Roadmap	18
4 Planning and implementing marketing and communication activities	20
4.1 Focus of marketing and communication activities.....	20
4.2 Communication alignment between Work Packages.....	20
4.3 Communication channels and KPIs.....	21
4.3.1 Project website and blog.....	24
4.3.2 Events participation and organisation.....	25
4.3.3 Marketing materials	28
4.3.4 Journals, publications and the press	29
4.3.5 Social media and newsletters.....	30
4.3.6 Links with national and international networks.....	31
4.4 KPI driven approach.....	31
5 Conclusions and next steps	35
ANNEX 1: Preliminary List of Stakeholders.....	36

Table of Figures

Figure 1 Science Mesh overview as main project asset.....	6
Figure 2 CS3MESH4EOSC project timeline.....	7
Figure 3 CS3MESH4EOSC key target stakeholders.....	9
Figure 4 Key messages for CS3MESH4EOSC stakeholders.....	11
Figure 5 CS3MESH4EOSC engagement levels and timeline.....	12
Figure 6 CS3MESH4EOSC communication roadmap and activities.....	18
Figure 7 CS3MESH4EOSC new website menu.....	24
Figure 8 CS3MESH4EOSC new website home page.....	25
Figure 9 CS3MESH4EOSC new marketing materials.....	29
Figure 10 Example of KPI “Flash Report”.....	32
Figure 11 Example of KPI Dashboard.....	32

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable details the activities to be carried out within Work Package 5 “Dissemination, Exploitation & Outreach”, which defines the communication strategy and stakeholder engagement plan for the project. The document will serve as a guide for the activities within CS3MESH4EOSC which aim to raise awareness about the project and its results among the target communities, so as to maximise the impact of communication efforts through stakeholder engagement activities.

The key target audiences for the communication and stakeholder engagement plan include the European scientific and academic community, institutional operators of services, software developers, and industrial communities.

Given that the involvement of early adopters and developers will be essential for the activities to be carried out in Work Package 2 (Information gathering on federated infrastructure development), Work Page 3 (Science Mesh technologies adopted and foundation standards and protocols implemented) and Work Package 4 (Applications to promote projects results), this deliverable already provides a clear strategy for engaging end users and developers and communicating their input to partners. As such the document constitutes a key reference point for all the expected results and assets that will come out of CS3MESH4EOSC by working transversally across all the WPs.

In this regard, weekly calls (STC) have been already set up to continuously gather information from all the WP leaders and advance/update the work on the communication and marketing strategy on a weekly basis. STC will also contribute to the editorial process by approving high relevant items in the communication and stakeholder engagement process (e.g. branding guidelines updates, website review, approval of relevant actions to be implemented, organisation of events, etc.). Furthermore, bi-weekly WP5 calls with representatives from all the WPs involved in the project will also be held to ensure cross-pollination and collection of results for further promotion.

1.2 Structure of the document

Starting with the overall communication and stakeholder engagement plan, the document is then structured in four main parts: goals and objectives; key target audiences; value propositions and key messages; stakeholder engagement strategy and KPIs. The text is complemented by a specific planning of all the communication and marketing activities to be implemented throughout the whole life span of the project, thus including a detailed timeline.

1.3 CS3MESH4EOSC main assets

The Science Mesh - pan-European storage and application service mesh. The main outcome from CS3MESH4EOSC will be a Pan-European natively FAIR and GDPR-compliant data store and sharing

Existing EOSC services and new ones integrated into the Science Mesh. As a final result, CS3MESH4EOSC assets will generate relevant benefits for the target communities by increasing the access and sharing of data, thus enabling researchers and industry to collaborate more effectively and retain control over their local data. Furthermore, the Science Mesh service will be interoperable with OpenAIRE tools, allowing metadata aggregation and direct export to OpenAIRE repositories such as Zenodo. All the actors in research and collaboration workflows will also be able to interact with each other without leaving their institution's service interface.

2 Marketing and communication strategy

The marketing and communication strategy is based on a set of specific steps that will ensure a comprehensive identification and achievement of the project results and benefits for the target communities. These include defining the communication and marketing goals, and the target audiences, and identifying the value proposition and key messages. The strategy is based on the SMART approach (specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, timely and targeted), which supports the subsequent planning and implementation of the marketing and communication activities, as well as the specific evaluation of the results achieved through detailed KPIs.

The strategy follows the project timeline, which is graphically presented below and is divided into three major phases.

Figure 2 CS3MESH4EOSC project timeline

Phase 1: from M1 to M12 is fully devoted to developing and testing the Science Mesh, creating the collaborative document workflow, and starting to invite early adopters to join the CS3MESH4EOSC community.

Phase 2: from M12 to M24 revolves around piloting Science Mesh in order to engage with a relevant set of potential vendors, as well as inviting other early adopters to join the CS3MESH4EOSC community.

Phase 3: from M24 to M36 aims to finalise the applications and to validate them in order to benefit from the full set of functionalities which the project will provide, and to further enlarge the community of users for consolidating the project's base technologies with other potential vendors.

2.1 CS3MESH4EOSC communication goals and objectives

The main objective of CS3MESH4EOSC is to allow European researchers - and the tech industry - to collaborate and work together by granting them access to a global collaboration platform integrated into their current working environments.

The benefits of CS3MESH4EOSC for the target communities will be:

- Seamless access to data and sharing, independently of where data is stored
- Interoperability of applications across vendors and mesh nodes
- Access to federated users' groups

Enabling researchers to efficiently synchronise, share and interact with vast data volumes will allow the CS3 community to generate a relevant Open Science paradigm shift.

The main objectives of the CS3MESH4EOSC communication & stakeholder engagement plan are thus the following:

- **Community building & stakeholder engagement:** identifying key target stakeholders for engagement in the project activities and events, developing timely and user-friendly communication of information, highlighting the benefits for each target group.
- **Communication & outreach:** regular awareness raising amongst key stakeholders and promotion of events & initiatives. The results of each phase of the project will be disseminated in a timely manner.
- **Knowledge transfer:** informing key stakeholders about the use and benefits of Science Mesh to improve the adoption of Open Science services, with a particular emphasis on research organisations and industry with similar data management requirements and constraints to be enrolled as early adopters.
- **Best Practices & Socio-economic Impact:** documenting & showcasing the value-added features of Science Mesh for the target communities and their socio-economic benefits.

2.2 Identifying the target audiences

A preliminary description of the target audiences for the project appears below. Marketing and communications plans to reach these groups are defined across project activities and will be regularly updated as the project progresses.

Figure 3 CS3MESH4EOSC key target stakeholders

More in detail, the main target audience of the project is composed by:

- **End-users & research communities:**
 - researchers and geographically distributed research groups
 - non-research users who need cross-institutional collaboration (e.g. administration collaborating on documents)
- **Institutional operators of services:**
 - system administrators and service managers who deploy and operate services
 - most of our project partners who make up a federated infrastructure
- **Commercial software developers:**
 - core sync/share development companies
 - vendors/companies developing other applications
- **Non-commercial software developers:**
 - development teams
 - general FOSS developers
- **Policy makers & citizens**
 - policy and decision makers
 - citizens
 - citizen scientists

2.3 Benefits and key messages to stakeholders

Value proposition and key messages for each stakeholder are defined below. These will be built around the following main topics: data sharing, open access, freedom of information, collaboration, increase of knowledge and better education. The current propositions included in this section for target audiences represent initial ideas which will be updated based on activities in the respective work packages. Defining the main benefits of the project for each stakeholder group is essential to be able to formulate the key messages. This first approach will be further updated throughout the project

lifetime as a collaborative effort between the project communications team and all the project partners.

Key benefits for the CS3MESH4EOSC targeted stakeholders

The added value of the project for the **end-users and research communities** is related to the capability to increase cross-institutional collaboration on sharing documents and enabling researchers to work, both independently and jointly, by using their domestic data without the need to register on an additional external platform.

The main benefit for the **institutional operators of services** is the opportunity for them to join the project as early adopters able to build sync & share capabilities through their already existing software platforms.

Commercial software developers will be offered new software applications not available on the market and will be allowed to sell this service to their target user communities.

The added value of the Science Mesh for the **non-commercial software developers** relies on the opportunity of being part of the Science Mesh by contributing to the integration of new application services.

Finally, **policy makers and citizens** will benefit from a service enabling digital sovereignty in policy making processes and effectively increasing both open access and human capital.

The key messages arising from the value propositions are depicted below.

Figure 4 Key messages for CS3MESH4EOSC stakeholders

2.4 Stakeholder engagement strategy and KPIs

CS3MESH4EOSC has identified a specific engagement strategy for each target audience. A detailed recruitment plan and activities for each stakeholder are presented in this section.

Before describing the CS3MESH4EOSC stakeholder engagement strategy, it is crucial to consider the different levels of engagement of the target audience in the various communication timeframes of the project. To achieve this goal, as pictured in the image below, we consider that **end-users and research communities** will be involved in the long term with a high level of communication activities, also after the end of the project as they constitute our target user base for the success of Science Mesh to be used at European level and beyond. In the first phase of the project, while we are still developing and finalising the deployment of the Science Mesh there will be a lower level of engagement of the end-users, which will intensify in Year 2.

With reference to the **institutional operators of services**, their involvement will be medium in terms of engagement activities as the project partners are already contributing to the Science Mesh and the system administrators and service manager are already engaged with the partner institutions. Their contribution to the project is expected to run in the medium term until the end of the project and hopefully they will keep using Science Mesh also after the end of the project.

The involvement of **commercial software developers** is crucial for the complete deployment of the Science Mesh at European and global level. A first set of vendors will start to be engaged with the project already from October 2020. The level of engagement planned will be very high from the outset and will persist until after the end of the project as the vendors contribute to extending this solution, thereby increasing our community user base.

The **non-commercial software developers** will be invited to contribute to the finalisation of the Science Mesh in the medium term and will be engaged in the project activities until Year 3.

The complete engagement of **policy makers and citizens** constitutes a long-term communication and involvement process that will continue also after the project ends.

Figure 5 CS3MESH4EOSC engagement levels and timeline

The recruitment plan below depicts the activities/channels to be implemented to engage the different target stakeholders. The plan includes all the activities to be developed to engage with the communities and is different from the communication plan which is described in the following section and aims to promote project results. A preliminary list of international organisations, private entities, institutions and communities to be involved in the project communication and marketing activities is included in Annex 1.

Channels	Goal	KPIS	Stakeholder category
Webinars	Invite early adopters to join the project and promote the benefits	- 3 webinars with 100 attendees in total (1/phase)	- End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services
Videos	Present the project main objectives, invite other stakeholders to join the community, show the results	- 3 videos (1/phase)	- End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services - Commercial and non-commercial software developers - Policy makers - Citizens
Podcasts	Discuss further improvements in Science Mesh at EU level and beyond	- 2 podcasts in total with at least 50 followers	- End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services
Blog articles	Attract newcomers and improve the research discussion about Open and FAIR data	- 1 content piece a week - At least 500 readers at the end of the project	- End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services - Commercial and non-commercial software developers - Policy makers - Citizens
F2F events	Present Science Mesh and related services	- 2 physical/digital events with 200 attendees in total	- End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services - Software development actors - Policy makers - Citizens

Channels	Goal	KPIS	Stakeholder category
Social media campaign	Attract newcomers and improve the research discussion about Open and FAIR data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5/week - 2000 followers on social media at the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services - Commercial and non-commercial software developers - Policy makers - Citizens
Newsletters	Invite stakeholders to join our events/webinars and contribute to the EU discourse on Open Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 200 stakeholders subscribed to the newsletter at the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services - Policy makers
Email marketing	Invite early adopters to join the project and promote the benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least 300 individual emails sent to potential interested early adopters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - End-users & research communities - Institutional operators of services

At the end of Phase 1 of the project, and extensively within the second phase, the community of Science Mesh will grow via the wide deployment of solutions outside the consortium to a group of “early adopters”. These include research organisations and industries wishing to become users of the services offered by Science Mesh. Regardless of whether or not they will become early adopters, research sector organisations and infrastructures are considered primary beneficiaries of the solutions developed.

Preliminary list of CS3MESH4EOSC early adopters

The University of Vienna is one of the oldest and largest universities in Europe: About 9,800 employees, 6,800 of whom are academics, work at 20 faculties and centres. This makes the University of Vienna Austria’s largest research and education institution: About 90,000 national and international students are currently enrolled at the University of Vienna.

Serving students, researchers, teachers and staff in the Education and Research community, RENATER offers a highly reliable and secure network simplifying collaboration and convergence in scientific and academic projects at the national level, but also at the European and international levels.

The Open Science Framework (OSF) is a tool that promotes open, centralized workflows by enabling capture of different aspects and products of the research lifecycle, including developing a research idea, designing a study, storing and analysing collected data, and writing and publishing reports or papers. It is developed and maintained by the Center for Open Science (COS), a non-profit organisation founded in 2013 that conducts research into scientific practice, builds and supports scientific research communities, and develops research tools and infrastructure to enable managing and archiving research.

EGI is the Federated e-Infrastructure set up to provide advanced computing services for research and innovation. EOSC-hub, a H2020 EINFRA-12 flagship EC project contributing to the European Open Science Cloud implementation coordinated by EGI is willing to promote the operational integration and exploitation of the CS3MESH4EOSC technologies and services for adoption by a large international group of users through the EOSC delivery channels. EOSC-hub will support the service management integration and delivery of CS3MESH4EOSC service.

Elettra is a multidisciplinary international research centre, specialised in generating high quality synchrotron and free-electron laser light and applying it in materials science. Its mission is to promote cultural, social and economic growth through basic and applied research; technical and scientific training; transfer of technology and know-how.

ESCAPE unites a cluster of ESFRI projects with similar challenges around data-driven research and demonstrated capabilities in addressing various stages of data workflow. All are concerned with fundamental research through complementary approaches. ESCAPE aims to produce versatile solutions, with great potential for discovery, to support the implementation of EOSC thanks to open data management, cross-border and multi-disciplinary open environment, according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles.

HIFIS aims to ensure an excellent information environment for outstanding research in all Helmholtz research fields and a seamless and performant IT-infrastructure connecting knowledge from all centres. It will build a secure and easy-to-use collaborative environment with efficiently accessible ICT services from anywhere. HIFIS will also support the development of research software with a high level of quality, visibility and sustainability.

ASTRON is developing a science data centre. In close collaboration with research institutes and data centres connected to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), ASTRON is unlocking the capabilities of existing and future research cloud infrastructure for its community, supporting the generation and sharing of high-quality scientific results openly.

ARCHIVER combines multiple ICT technologies, including extreme data-scaling, network connectivity, service interoperability, and business models, in a hybrid cloud environment to deliver end-to-end archival and preservation services that cover the full research lifecycle. By acting as a collective of procurers, ARCHIVER

creates an eco-system for specialist ICT companies active in archiving, who would like to introduce new services capable of supporting the expanding needs of research communities.

CS3MESH4EOSC & THE CS3 COMMUNITY

CS3MESH4EOSC is a natural evolution of the experiences gained during the CS3 conferences over the past 5 years throughout Europe. Within the CS3 community, there is an urgent demand from researchers, educators and students across Europe to use sync&share EU-based services for international collaboration.

The current lack of integration of the CS3 services also currently constitutes an Impediment to researchers taking advantage of cloud computing services for data storage and sharing. Through the involvement of the CS3 community in the Science Mesh, CS3MESH4EOSC will provide an effective solution to this issue, thus allowing for the integration of new application services - even those developed at other sites and using different technology solutions - while drastically reducing service costs.

To this end, the CS3 Community will be involved both by engaging its developers for the development of the Science Mesh, and as an end-user to validate the Science Mesh service offering. Furthermore, CS3 community services providers are already part of the CS3MESH4EOSC consortium and many more from NRENs and e-Infrastructure will join the project as early adopters.

CS3MESH4EOSC & EOSC

The CS3MESH4EOSC project aims to constitute a natural vehicle for public awareness in order to attract and engage with a wide pan-European research community, as well as involving promising researchers in improving Open Science in the EU.

To further strengthen this strategy, the CS3MESH4EOSC project will seek to involve all relevant services using EOSC as the main contact point. This mechanism will also create an opportunity to further Increase awareness of personal data protection among the wider user community and service providers.

Engaging researchers, developers, and professionals involved in EOSC is vital for CS3MESH4EOSC in terms of linking different communities and enabling them to collaborate.

The outreach strategy of EOSC with the CS3MESH4EOSC project will include specific dissemination and communication activities, such as:

- Involvement of the EOSC communities in specific targeted webinars for developers and researchers (at least 1 webinar every 4 months).
- Generation of news content relevant for the EOSC communities and included in the blog section of the CS3MESH4EOSC website (at least 1 news per week). Similar messages to be distributed via the social media channels of the CS3MESH4EOSC project as well.
- Organisation of a bi-monthly meeting with the EOSC board for alignment of activities and key communication messages to disseminate to the wider CS3MESH4EOSC and EOSC communities.

- Creation of a podcast targeted to EOSC communities and focused on the development of new services based on the Science Mesh APIs (1 every 2 months).
- Targeted online marketing campaigns and specific newsletters to involve the EOSC communities in the CS3MESH4EOSC project activities (on the basis of the needs identified in the stakeholder communities through surveys and one to one meetings).

3 CS3MESH4EOOSC Communication & Marketing Roadmap

The communication timeline has been created to align with the different phases of the Science Mesh development and is constituted by 5 main steps. The steps in the CS3MESH4EOOSC communication and marketing implementation plan are highlighted in yellow in the image below.

Figure 6 CS3MESH4EOOSC communication roadmap and activities

More in detail, the communication and marketing implementation plan is constituted by these steps:

- 1. Preliminary Comms & Marketing Strategy:** the first phase of the project has been devoted to developing a visual identity for the project along with first versions of the logos and website. Also, during the first 8 months of the project, the social media accounts (Twitter and LinkedIn) were set up and sharing of project information initiated. This first phase has been focused on promoting the project objectives and expected impact to the wider research community.
- 2. Second version of Comms & Marketing Strategy:** in the second step, this new version of the communication and marketing strategy has been developed and includes a stakeholder map plus detailed plans for reaching the defined target audiences. We have also reviewed the visual identify and present a second set of branding guidelines in Section 4.3.3 below, and a new proposed structure for the CS3MESH4EOOSC website. Two new versions of the project logo have also been created and integrated into social media channels. An extensive social media campaign was started in September 2020 with one post a day. The next three months will be focused on bringing the new CS3MESH4EOOSC website online (by the end of September 2020) and promoting the initial project results in order to showcase Science Mesh to the key target stakeholders in academia and industry and to software developers,. Channels to be used are principally the project website, social media, the CS3MESH4EOOSC blog, and a newsletter. To showcase the impact of the project on Open Science, a first video will be created for the research community and uploaded to the project website and to Youtube.
- 3. Stakeholder engagement for adoption of Science Mesh:** the third stage will be completely focused on increasing the number of early adopters of Science Mesh, in order to test the platform and start to involve a restricted number of potential vendors. During this phase,

project communications will revolve around promoting the Science Mesh services extensively to research and industrial key stakeholders by using social media channels, as well as webinars, podcasts, email marketing, newsletters, events and face-to-face or online meetings. A second video will be created with interviews of early adopters in order to encourage others to join the projects and test Science Mesh.

4. **Community Engagement:** this step will aim at concretely engaging the adopter community with the services deployed by the project. This phase will take advantage of webinars, presentations at events, newsletters, email marketing and dedicated events, as well as social media campaigns. In this phase, policy makers and international networks will be proactively engaged by organising online policy dialogues and joint sessions at international events, and through press releases.
5. **Impact & Sustainability:** this final stage will aim at ensuring and increasing the impact of Science Mesh in the long term and after the project ends. To this end, a final conference will be organised to present the project's results and expected long-term impact. Policy makers and international networks previously involved during stage four will be invited to attend this event, and the early adopters will present the impacts Science Mesh on their daily practices in the past months. A final video of the project will be created to promote the project results through the CS3MESH4EOSC website and social media channels. Other relevant communication and marketing channels to be used to promote the project results and impacts within this phase are joint sessions at international events, newsletters, press releases, the project website, face-to-face meetings, social media channels, and the blog. This stage also includes the identification of motivational drivers for the relevant research and industrial communities to be engaged in the long term within the Science Mesh (e.g. reputational drivers, rewards & incentives, financial drivers, etc).

4 Planning and implementing marketing and communication activities

4.1 Focus of marketing and communication activities

Based on the defined objectives, target audiences and key messages, the communication plan of CS3MESH4EOSC focuses on:

- Attracting the target audiences to achieve high impact on researchers, academia, students, software developers, libraries and archives, policy makers, citizens, as well as project partners.
- Showcasing the implementation of the pan-European Science Mesh in other local, regional, national and international contexts.
- Disseminating the project results and major achievements throughout the lifespan of the project.
- Influencing the political and industrial spheres at European and international level with strong focus on open access and data sharing.
- Collaborating and aligning with other EU projects, international networks and related initiatives.

The marketing and communication plan devoted to promoting CS3MESH4EOSC will be focused on the following main activities:

- Creating/updating the project brand and communication tools, channels and main communication activities.
- Setting up a team to coordinate the marketing and communication activities. The communication team is having regular telcos on a need-to basis.
- Creating communication processes to ensure good information flow between the partners and communication representatives of the project. Both an internal communication list and a specific mailing list will be created for external and project-internal use (hosted on CERN premises) for any communication-related correspondence.
- Generating a new website and regularly updating information there and on the blog.
- Developing multi-language communication materials, tools and campaigns, to support the promotion of the project to the target audiences and the stakeholder engagement activities.
- Creating and managing a set of social media channels (list included in the section below) to create a solid online marketing strategy, considering existing channels at international and local level.
- Organising key industrial/market-oriented events and fairs targeted to outreach industrial partners and entrepreneurs.
- Setting up relevant channels to reach the policy makers, such as Policy Dialogues, events (mainly digital), and Policy Briefs to disseminate as much policy-related results as widely as possible.

4.2 Communication alignment between Work Packages

To ensure effective communication and marketing activities, alignment between the different Work

Packages is essential, not only in terms of identifying key messages to promote, but also to provide a coherent framework for gathering project results to be communicated to the target audience s.

To this end, relevant internal activities developed by CS3MESH4EOSC in each Work Package will be identified and each result will be shared with the communication team (both as a recording of online activities or in documentation format for offline work) so they can promote it on the main project social media channel feeds, website and blog. This approach also allows the project to ensure no Work Package works "in a silo" and both internal and external communications are smooth and coherent.

An internal wiki platform hosted by CERN collects all the updates from each Work Package, and a specific bi-weekly call from Work Package 5 will be organised in order to discuss relevant updates from partners to be published on our communication channels, along with the weekly Steering Committee calls.

A weekly news sheet will be used for planning and reporting on content and will be shared externally. Each partner will be invited to contribute to the creation of content to be shared with the communication team, which will review it and prepare it for publication online. Both technical and marketing staff will be assigned to each newspiece. Specific deadlines for internal and final release of each item will be defined.

4.3 Communication channels and KPIs

The CS3MESH4EOSC project will use an effective mix of **communication channels** to reach the previously identified target audiences. In the table below all the dissemination channels for each target audience of the project are presented alongside the dissemination level and expected KPIs.

Channel(s)	Local level	International level	Target Audience	KPIs
<i>Website and blog</i>	The project website/blog and partners' own online presence, plus local networks' websites	The project website/blog and links with other international networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial and non-commercial software developers • Policy makers • Citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100.000+ pageviews at the end of the project • At least 1 piece of news included in the blog per week
<i>Research Conferences and industrial fairs</i>	Participation in local, regional and national conferences	Participation in international conferences and roadshows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial software developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In total project partners will participate in 20+ online and/or in presence conferences/fairs
<i>Organisation of events</i>	Organisation of local workshops	Organisation of a Final Conference and other promotional events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial and non-commercial software developers • Policy makers • Citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of at least 2 major project events reaching 150 potential stakeholders (online)
<i>Marketing materials</i>	Materials to be shared in local events by the project partners and local networks	Promotional materials to be shared in international conferences, as well as online promotional material (videos)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial and non-commercial software developers • Policy makers • Citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 flyers • 1 roll-up • 200 branded post-its • 1 e-book • 3 videos • 3 podcasts

Channel/s	Local level	International level	Target Audience	KPIs
<i>Journals and publications/ press releases</i>	Local specialised magazines and newspapers	International peer reviewed scientific journals, magazines, book chapters and conferences. Featured stories will target publications in magazines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 publications in total in peer reviewed journals • 3 press releases • 6 publications and articles • At least 10 public reports on Zenodo/OpenAIRE
<i>Social media and newsletters</i>	Local stakeholders' social media channels (e.g. networks, organisations, etc.)	Facebook, LinkedIn, Youtube/Vimeo social media channels of the project, plus project partners' channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial and non-commercial software developers • Policy makers • Citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1000 twitter followers • 500+ LinkedIn connections • 300+ views of videos on Youtube/Vimeo • 200+ subscribers to the newsletter • At least 1 post published every week on social media
<i>Webinars and podcasts</i>		On demand activities for the communities involved on specific targeted topics (e.g. how to use and improve Science Mesh)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial and non-commercial software developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 webinars (with at least 150 people in total) • 2 podcasts (reaching at least 100 people in total)
<i>National and international networks</i>	National industry and research associations/networks	International industry associations, research associations and networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-users & research communities • Institutional operators of services • Commercial and non-commercial software developers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link with 30+ national and international networks

Table 1. Communication channels and KPIs

4.3.1 Project website and blog

The project website will contain updated information about the project, a blog section for news, events, videos, social media plugins, newsletter area (with a link to subscribe the newsletter), project library with a media kit and publications (including deliverables), as well as an internal space for project partners and communities.

The CS3MESH4EOSC website will allow visitors to contact the project via a specific form. Questions will be directed to communication representatives. A temporary project website has been created (and is available here <https://cs3mesh4eosc.eu/>) to ensure a solid reference point for the expected target audiences. This website consists of basic information about the project, links to social media, and contact information. An updated version of the website will be available by the end of September 2020, as well as a mailing list plugin enabling the project to start collecting a contact list for future newsletters and other external, email-based communication. Moreover, the CS3MESH4EOSC website will be linked directly with Science Mesh, which will also be offered as part of the EOSC-hub and integrated with its existing portfolio of services.

. A preliminary navigation tree for the new website is presented below:

Figure 7 CS3MESH4EOSC new website menu

The home page of the website will also be restructured in order to immediately highlight all the relevant information that should be promoted to the different categories of key stakeholders throughout the project lifetime. In the figure below, we show the new structure of the home page envisioned by the CS3MESH4EOSC project partners.

Figure 8 CS3MESH4EOOSC new website home page

4.3.2 Events participation and organisation

The table below provides a sample of available international conferences, workshops and summits for contributions and participation of CS3MESH4EOOSC partners (not exhaustive, most relevant in bold).

Event	Date	Link	Target audience
<i>JAX London 2020</i>	5-8 October 2020	https://jaxlondon.com/	Software developers, research communities, industrial research
<i>IEEE Cloud 2020</i>	19-23 October 2020	https://conferences.computer.org/cloud/2020/	Research communities, industrial research, software developers

Event	Date	Link	Target audience
<i>EOSC Symposium</i>	19-22 October 2020	https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/news-opinion/save-date-eosc-symposium-2020	Researchers, data scientists, e-Infrastructures, Research Infrastructures, EOSC projects, EOSC Working Group members
<i>eResearch Australasia</i>	19-23 October 2020	https://conference.eresearch.edu.au	Research communities, industrial research, policy makers
<i>CLOUD COMPUTING 2020</i>	25-29 October 2020	https://www.iaria.org/conferences2020/CLOUDCOMPUTING20.html	Research communities, industrial research, policy makers
<i>CloudConf 2020</i>	5 November 2020	https://2020.cloudconf.it	Research communities, industrial research
<i>ICCWS 2020: 14th International Conference on Cloud and Web Services</i>	9-10 November 2020	https://waset.org/cloud-and-web-services-conference-in-november-2020-in-dubai	Research communities, industrial research, policy makers
<i>RDA Plenary Meeting</i>	9-12 November 2020	https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-16th-plenary-meeting-costa-rica-virtual	Research communities, industrial research, policy makers
<i>ICDCIS 2020: 14th International Conference on Data, Computing and Information Sciences</i>	26-27 November 2020	https://waset.org/data-computing-and-information-sciences-conference-in-november-2020-in-jerusalem	Research communities, industrial research, policy makers
<i>CCIS 2021</i>	5-7 January 2021	https://www.seminarjan.org/conference/CCIS2021/	Research communities, software developers
<i>ICESAC 2021: 15th International Conference on E-Science and Advanced Computing</i>	18-19 January 2021	https://waset.org/e-science-and-advanced-computing-conference-in-january-2021-in-rome	Research communities, software developers

Event	Date	Link	Target audience
<i>FOSDEM 2021</i>	6-7 February 2021	https://fosdem.org/2021/	Software developers
<i>CTCCC 2021</i>	17-19 March 2021	http://www.ctccc.org	Research communities, industrial research
International Symposium on Grids & Clouds 2021 (ISGC 2021)	21-26 March 2021	https://indico4.twgrid.org/indico/event/14/	Research communities, industrial research
<i>CLOSER 2021</i>	28-30 April 2021	http://closer.scitevents.org	Research communities, industrial research
<i>Open Repositories 2021</i>	May 31 – June 3 2020	https://or2020.sun.ac.za	Research communities, software developers
<i>Linux Conference</i>	23-25 January 2021	https://lca2021.linux.org.au	Software developers
<i>EUNIS CONGRESS 2021</i>	9-11 June 2021	https://www.eunis.org/calendar/eunis-annual-congress-2021/	Research communities, industrial research
<i>TNC21</i>	21-25 June 2021	https://www.geant.org/News_and_Events/Events/TNC	Research communities, industrial research
<i>Codemotion Amsterdam</i>	May 27-28 2021	https://events.codemotion.com/conferences/amsterdam/2020/news/codemotion-amsterdam-postponed-to-spring-2021/	Software developers
<i>Asia Pacific Advanced Network (APAN)</i>	August/ September 2021	https://apan.net/allmeetings	Research communities, industrial research
<i>DeiC Conference 2021</i>	3-4 November 2021	https://www.deic.dk/en/deic.dk/en/conference/2020	Research communities, industrial research

Table 1. Events and conferences list

In addition to the participation in international conferences and fairs, the project will organise a series of digital events (webinars, online conferences, etc.) in order to engage with the target communities. Planning participation in events is the responsibility of the communications team. A shared events sheet will be used for planning and reporting on events organisation and participation and partners

invited to contribute. The content will range from worldwide events to internal events and meetings, as well as events organised in local areas.

4.3.3 Marketing materials

Specific marketing material will be designed and produced for the main events. This will include roll-ups, badges, agendas, goody bags, stickers and brochures to be shared both in local/national events, as well as international conferences. For the local events, the material will be translated to local languages. The marketing materials will carefully follow the branding and visual identity of the project.

A new version of the branding guidelines has been produced for CS3MESH4EOSC and includes a new logo package, an updated colour-palette along with the new typography base, an updated Powerpoint template for presentations, and new visual branding for both Twitter and LinkedIn. The full branding guideline is included as Annex 2 of this deliverable. Below we provide some visuals of the main marketing materials created.

Figure 9 CS3MESH4EOOSC new marketing materials

4.3.4 Journals, publications and the press

Local specialised magazines and newspapers will be used as channels to disseminate the project results and increase its visibility among the targeted audience in a particular area. The articles and press releases will be translated to local languages. In addition to the local channels, the project intends to disseminate its innovative results in international peer-reviewed scientific journals, in magazines and book chapters, and at conferences. Featured stories will target publications in relevant local and international magazines. In the table below a list (non-exhaustive) of targeted publications in peer-reviewed journals is provided.

European & International press/media channels and scientific journals

MyScienceWork, sciDev, Digital Meets Culture, CORDIS Wire & CORDIS News, DSM Newsletter, EC Research and Innovation Press Centre, EU Agenda & European Agenda, EurActiv, PRLog and PRWeb, DG CNECT newsletter, Noodles, Europost, Tom's Hardware, Firmenpresse.de, Startupbusiness Network, Wallstreet Online, NUANCE (Newsletter of UbuntuNet Alliance), CONNECT (Magazine from the GEANT Community), CAAST-Net PLUS Magazine, CG Channel, Make, Technology News, DCI, WorldNewsPress.net, Webnuz, New York Social Diary, Before It's News, Sina English, Voices - Sun Times, The Central News Agency, Bizcommunity.com, Copernicus Observer, International innovation, ComputerWeekly, 24n.biz (UK) , Computer World UK, eWeek Europe, EUObserver, EURACTIV, Government Tehcnology, Hostingtechnews.com, HPC in the cloud, HPC Wire, Innovations report, InfoWorld. DataCenterDynamics, Journal of Cloud Computing: Advances, Systems and Applications, International Journal of Cloud Computing, Internet of Things and Cloud Computing, IEEE Cloud Computing, International Journal of Distributed and Cloud Computing, Science Business, Science Europe, INASP, e-IRG, Research EU Magazine, Journal of Web Engineering, Journal of Web Semantics (JWS), Journal on Digital Libraries (IJDL), ScienceNode, Nature.

4.3.5 Social media and newsletters

The following social media channels will be set up for the project external communication:

- Twitter - @CS3MESH4EOSC.
- LinkedIn – a page is available here <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cs3mesh4eosc>.
- YouTube/Vimeo - channel for CS3MESH4EOSC - to be created soon.

A specific short social media guide (visual identity) will be created and shared with project partners to advise on the usage of CS3MESH4EOSC social media channels including also some general and useful tips on social media. This guide will also be regularly updated during the project lifetime as the usage of channels evolves based on the marketing and communication needs of the project.

The project newsletters will be disseminated to relevant stakeholders using Mailchimp and a dedicated mailing list. Newsletters and marketing materials will also be promoted through the social media channels.

Relevant EU twitter accounts in the domain of the Open Science, Cloud Computing and FAIR data for Horizon 2020

@Horizon2020EU, @EU_H2020, @H2020SME, @ICTinnovEU @DigitalAgendaEU (For H2020/research/innovation); @ICT_IDEALIST ; @CloudforEurope, @SPARC_EU, @ProjectOpenUP, @GEANTNews, @OpenAIRE_eu, @PRACE_RI, @DI4R_eu, @nectar_cloud, @ReteGARR, @INCForg, @eGov_EU, @NetTechEU, @EUeic, @EU_opendata, @CamOpenData, @opendatacharter, @openforcefield, @journalopenhw, @ORION_opensci, @ORCID_Org, @INOSproject, @opencloudmesh, @EASSH, @eoscpilot, @FIT4RRIEU, @fosterscience, @ScienceEurope, @ESCAPE_EU, @ArchiverProject, @EOSC_DIH, @NI4OS_eu, @CERICnews, @ERIC_forum, @essneutron, @ExPaNDs_EU, @SSHOpenCloud, @BlueCloudEU, @Panosc_eu, @EoscLife, @ESFRI_eu, @ENVRIcomm, @digitalities, @indigodatacloud, @OCREproject, @TheSandbioxGame, @EUCitSciProject, @euatweets, @EuCitSci, @COOperas, @ISC, @atp, @ERC_Research, @ResearchDataUoE, @EUScienceInnov, @DigiSovrgntyCo, @CWInI, @ODISSEI_nl, @SURF_NL, @nl_rse, @AeRO_eResearch, @qcifltd, @EU_ScienceHub, @DSMeu, @FutureTechEU, @_open_science_, @CEGA_UC, @EO_OPEN_SCIENCE, @ESAOpenSci, @SciOpenness, @aaas, @dri_ireland, @openscience_in, @ro_openscience, @NGI4eu, @esfdsev, @PRACE_RI, @DeffOPERA, @NCInews, @GEANTnews, @DOAJplus, @CrossrefOrg, @datacite, @OpenSciTalk, @resdatall, @irods, @Cos4Cloud, @SWITCH_ch, @ARDC_AU, @EoscPillar, @OpenSciPlatform, @OSFramework, @Science_Open, @openscience, @ZENODO_ORG, @d4science, @euospp, @LOVocabularies, @DataSciSchools, @EOSC_synergy, @EOSC_Nordic, @FAISFAIR_EU, @EoscPortal, @CoreTrustSeal, @EGI_eInfra, @ownCloud, @Nextclouders, @GOFAIRofficial, @Eudat_eu, @REfieldstories, @eScienceCenter, @SURF_onderzoek, @CERN, @AARNet, @DigiGav, @Panosc @LIBEREurope @Ditigalcuratation @BDVA_PPP, @enisa_eu, @HolaCloud @Joinup_eu

EU twitter accounts relevant in the ICT policy field
@DSMeu, @eInfraEU, @ViolaRoberto, @DIGITconf, @EU_Commission, @EU_ScienceHub, @ICTscienceEU, @Inno4Europe, @EU_DataPortal, @EUDataEcosystem, @OpenForumEurope, @JunckerEU
ICT journals
@DataconomyMedia, @ert_eu, @WSJD, @tech_eu, @digital_eu , @FigaroTech, @ReutersTech , @ResearchGate , @EUhorizon2020, @EU_RESEARCH, @PublicTech , @BBCTech, @euronewsknwlge, @SciNode, @ScienceInEurope , @cordiseurope , @myCORDIS , @WIRED , @HPCwire , @TomTaborHPC @JRussonHPC @TiffanyTrader@Computing_News , @Cloud_Zone, @cloudcompah , , @TheCloudNetwork, @CloudComputing3 @EduCloud

4.3.6 Links with national and international networks

In addition to the specific CS3MESH4EOSC channels, the project will benefit from liaising with relevant national and international networks, in some cases connected with project partners. These include, among others, the channels listed below.

International networks
CESSDA, EOSC Nordic, Open Science Framework, researchobject.org, Research Data Alliance, FAIMS, Spoman Open Science, EOSC-HUB, EOSC Secretariat, EOSC Enhance, FAIRSFair, The e-Infrastructure Reflection Group (eIRG) and National Governments for e-Infrastructure, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), the EIROforum organisations, Helix-Nebula, PICSE, WLCG, CloudWATCH, EOSC Pilot, EOSC Portal, CS3, GÉANT, ELETTRA, ESCAPE, ARCHIVER, EGI, Open Science Mesh, ASTRON, Open Science Framework, Sciebo, D4Science

4.4 KPI driven approach

Evaluation of the communication and marketing activities will be based on several parameters. Measurable impacts (KPIs) are tracked on a monthly basis through a “Flash Report” monitoring the visibility, engagement, and dissemination potential of online activities using automated software which extracts, analyses, and visualises the selected figures.

An online Dashboard will be set up to display the project's online presence and the community's engagement with it.

The publication of articles, reports, magazines and white papers consumed by researcher communities will also be monitored.

Type	KPI	Target Y1	Target Y2	Target by the end of the project	Total (1st YEAR)	April 2020	May 2020	June 2020	July 2020	August 2020	September 2020	1st YEAR
Website & Consultation Platform												
G	Website Visitors	3600	8400	14400	2075	2075						2075
-	Sessions	9600	19200	28800	3971	3971						3971
G	Interviews/Blogposts			30	5	5						5
-	Interviews/blogposts from different stakeholders from different			10	0							0
Press releases & papers												
G	Dissemination of technical results through peer-reviewed co			4	0	0						0
G	N° responses on Blue-Cloud Roadmap Consultation (per co		75-100		0	0						0
G	Fact Sheets to summarise what the pilot blue cloud can offe			15	0	0						0
Communication Material												
-	N° Flyers			4	1	1						1
-	N° Posters			4	1	1						1
-	Rollup banners			2	1	1						1
-	Presentations			50	0							0
-	Give aways			2	2	2						2
-	Newsletters	4	8	12	0	0						0
Social Media												
-	Twitter followers			1000	393	393						393
-	Twitter impressions			700000	0							0
-	N° tweets			700	283	283						283
-	LinkedIn followers			200	62	62						62
-	LinkedIn impressions			100000	0							0
G	YouTube Videos			6	6	6						6
-	Youtube Views			500	0							0
-	Social Media followers			2000	0							0
Events & Webinars												
G	N° webinars (with at least 30 participants)			10	0	0						0
G	Presence at 3rd party events (physical and virtual)			50	0	0						0
G	N° participants in virtual hackathon (minimum)			100	0	0						0
G	Blue-Cloud Open Workshop (with at least 50 participants)			2	0	0						0
G	Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshop			2	0	0						0
G	N° participants at Blue-Cloud final event			100	0	0						0
Stakeholders												
G	N° synergies			10	4	4						4
G	Contact database	500	1200	2000	0							0
Milestones												
G	MS24 Blue-Cloud Branding (M1)			1	1	1						1
G	MS25 Blue-Cloud Web platform release #1 (M3)			1	1	1						1
G	MS26 Blue-Cloud Webinars (M10)			1	0	0						0
G	MS27 Blue-Cloud Webinars (M12)			1	0	0						0
G	MS36 Organisation & roll-out of Blue-Cloud Workshops & Post-Event Reports (1st event) (M14)			1	0	0						0
G	MS39 Organisation & roll-out of Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshops & Post-Event Reports (1st workshop) (M14)			1	0	0						0
G	MS28 Blue-Cloud Webinars (M15)			1	0	0						0
G	MS29 Blue-Cloud Webinars (M17)			1	0	0						0
G	MS30 Blue-Cloud Webinars (M20)			1	0	0						0
G	MS37 Organisation & roll-out of Blue-Cloud Workshops & Post-Event Reports (2nd event) (M22)			1	0	0						0
G	MS44 Organisation & roll-out of Blue-Cloud Roadmap Workshops +Post-Event Reports (2nd workshop) (M22)			1	0	0						0

Figure 10 Example of KPI “Flash Report”

Figure 11 Example of KPI Dashboard

In the table below we have included a specific timeline of the communication and marketing activities to be developed from M9 to M18.

Project phase	Time Period	Activities	
Building the Science Mesh Science Mesh promotional campaign	September 2020	<u>Branding</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Logo pack and new branding guidelines, marketing materials (ppt template) <u>Website</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wireframes of the new structure and new website development & population <u>Deliverables</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> D5.1 Communication and stakeholder engagement plan <u>Video</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Script for presenting the Science Mesh in the first video <u>Youtube:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of the project channel 	<p style="text-align: center;">Horizontal Activities</p> <p>Website: 1x content piece weekly</p> <p>Twitter posting: 5x weekly</p> <p>Linkedin posting: 3x weekly</p> <p>Conferences, fairs, trades: 1 bi-monthly</p> <p>KPI monitoring: 1x Monthly</p>
	October 2020	<u>Collaterals</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> General flyer and a rollup banner <u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 article per week <u>Newsletter</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 bi-monthly 	
	November 2020	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 article per week 	
	December 2020	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 article per week <u>Newsletter</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 bi-monthly <u>Webinars</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 for early adopters <u>Press release</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 presenting the project results in the first 12 months and the Science Mesh 	

Project phase	Time Period	Activities	
Stakeholder engagement for Adoption Campaign	January 2021	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 article per week <u>Collaterals</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science Mesh Services flyer and a rollup banner with services 	<p style="text-align: center;">Horizontal Activities</p> <p>Website: 1x content piece weekly</p> <p>Twitter posting: 5x weekly</p> <p>Linkedin posting: 3x weekly</p> <p>Conferences, fairs, trades: 1 bi-monthly</p> <p>KPI monitoring: 1x Monthly</p>
	February 2021	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 article per week <u>Newsletter</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 bi-monthly • 	
	March 2021	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 article per week <u>Webinars</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 for commercial and non-commercial software developers 	
	April 2021	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 article per week <u>Newsletter</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 bi-monthly 	
	May 2021	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 article per week <u>E-mail marketing</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly for vendors <u>Podcasts</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 for engaging with new adopters 	
	June 2021	<u>Blog</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 article per week <u>Newsletter</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 bi-monthly <u>E-mail marketing</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 bi-weekly for vendors <u>Video:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 with interviews to the Community 	

5 Conclusions and next steps

This document has presented the communication and stakeholder engagement plan of the CS3MESH4EOSC project, and includes a set of activities to be undertaken in the upcoming months, along with relevant KPIs to be considered for monitoring progress. It provides the foundation to guide project partners and the communication team in starting to organise all the communication, dissemination and marketing activities necessary to promote the project results and achievements.

A second version of the document is not foreseen at the moment. However, should an update be deemed necessary later in the project, more information will be added to Deliverables D5.2 and D5.3 Report on Dissemination & exploitation of Project Results. Feedback from project partners will be taken into account regarding potential improvements.

ANNEX 1: Preliminary List of Stakeholders

Stakeholder	Name	Link
Academia	GO-FAIR	https://www.go-fair.org
	GÉANT	https://www.geant.org
	CS3	https://www.cs3community.org
	OpenAIRE	https://www.openaire.eu
	EduGAIN	https://edugain.org
	INFN-BOX	https://agenda.infn.it/event/10802/contributions/5364/attachments/3977/4379/INFN_box_CCR_Maggio.pdf
	ETH ZURICH	https://ethz.ch/de.html
	Sciebo	https://www.sciebo.de
	LMU	https://www.uni-muenchen.de/index.html
	LOV OKFN	lov.okfn.org
	D4Science	d4science.org
	FAIRDATA FI	Fairdata.fi
	Center for Open Science	cos.io
	EPFL Open Science	https://www.epfl.ch/research/open-science/
	The European University Association	https://eua.eu/issues/21:open-science.html
	ZENODO	zenodo.org
	JRC	ec.europa.eu/jrc
	Industry and developers	EGI
CORE TRUST SEAL		https://www.coretrustseal.org
OwnCloud		https://owncloud.com
NextCLOUD		https://nextcloud.com
SeaFILE		https://www.seafile.com/en/home/
DESYCLOUD		https://desycloud.desy.de/index.php
PYDIO		https://pydio.com
DROPBOX		https://www.dropbox.com
SWITCHDRIVE		https://www.switch.ch/drive/
SURF DRIVE		https://www.surf.nl/en/surfdrive-store-and-share-your-files-securely-in-the-cloud
Open Science		https://twitter.com/openscience
Science Open		scienceopen.com
Open Science Platform		pon.edu.pl
ODISSEI		odissei-data.nl
POWERFOLDER		https://www.powerfolder.com

Stakeholder	Name	Link
Policy makers	EOSC-hub	https://www.eosc-hub.eu
	EOSC Secretariat	https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/
	EOSC Portal	https://www.eosc-portal.eu
	OCRE	https://www.ocre-project.eu
	ESCAPE	https://projectescape.eu
	ARCHIVER	https://archiver-project.eu
	EUDAT	https://www.eudat.eu
	FAIRSFair	https://www.fairsfair.eu
	RDA EUROPE	http://europe.rd-alliance.org
	Reinforce EU	reinforceeu.eu
	European Open Science Policy Platform	https://twitter.com/euospp
	Data Sharing Coalition	datasharingcoalition.eu
	Open Science Newsletter	osnewsletter.wordpress.com
	OPENDEI	https://www.opendei.eu
Citizens	DataSci Schools	https://twitter.com/DataSciSchools
	ECSA Citizen Science	https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/working-groups/citizen-science-and-open-science/
	FOSTER Citizen Science	https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/taxonomy/term/245

ANNEX 2: CS3MESH4EOSC NEW BRAND GUIDELINE

BRAND GUIDELINE

THE DEFINITION OF THE BRAND
BRAND GUIDELINES V1.0 2020

CS3MESH4EOSC

FRAGMENTATION OF FILE AND
APPLICATION SERVICES, DIGITAL
SOVEREIGNTY AND THE APPLI-
CATION OF FAIR PRINCIPLES IN
THE EVERYDAY PRACTICE OF
RESEARCHERS.

RESPONSIBLE AGENCY :
TRUST-IT Services

CREATION DATE :
SEPTEMBER 2020

BRAND MANUAL

CS3MESH4EOSC

FRAGMENTATION OF FILE AND APPLICATION SERVICES, DIGITAL SOVEREIGNTY AND THE APPLICATION OF FAIR PRINCIPLES IN THE EVERYDAY PRACTICE OF RESEARCHERS.

RESPONSIBLE AGENCY :
TRUST-IT Services

CREATION DATE :
SEPTEMBER 2020

Table of content

Sec.01 Brand Logo	03
Sec.02 Brand Color	05
Sec.03 Brand Typography	07
Sec.04 Brand Social	09
Sec.05 Brand Presentation	11

A large, faint, stylized logo watermark is visible in the background, consisting of a thick, rounded rectangular border with a decorative, scalloped top edge. The text "CORPO-RATE LOGO" is centered within this watermark.

CORPO- RATE LOGO

Brand Logo

SEC.01

01. CORPORATE LOGO

COMPACT VERSION

EXTENDED VERSION

DARK GREY BACKGROUND

LIGHT GREY BACKGROUND

PRIMARY COLOR BACKGROUND

SECONDARY COLOR BACKGROUND

01.2 INCORRECT LOGO APPLICATIONS

COLOR PALETTE

Brand Color

SEC.02

02

THE PRIMARY COLORS

LIGHT BLUE

PANTONE 109-14 C
RGB R31 G145 B204
HEX/HTML #1F91CC
CMYK C77 M30 Y3 K0

COLD GREY

PANTONE 174-15 C
RGB R69 G74 B84
HEX/HTML #454A54
CMYK C71 M58 Y56 K42

02.1

THE SECONDARY COLORS

ORANGE

PANTONE 20-16 C
RGB R223 G129 B10
HEX/HTML #DF810A
CMYK C10 M56 Y100 K1

DARK HOT GREY

PANTONE 178-15 C
RGB R85 G79 B69
HEX/HTML #554F45
CMYK C56 M50 Y58 K50

TYPHO- GRAPHY BASE

Brand Fonts

SEC.03

03

MAIN FONT (TITLES)

Aa.

Avant Garde // 0123456789

REGULAR

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ

BOLD

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ

03.1

SECONDARY FONT (DESCRIPTIONS)

Aa.

Calibri // 0123456789

REGULAR

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ

BOLD

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNopQRSTUVWXYZ

SOCIAL NET- WORK

Brand Social

SEC.04

04

NEW SOCIAL NETWORK IDENTITY

LINKEDIN COVER

TWITTER COVER

LINKEDIN & TWITTER POST

PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

Brand Presentation

SEC.05

05

POWER POINT MASTER TEMPLATE

FIRST SLIDE

CS³ MESH⁴ EOOSC
Connecting European Data

CS3MESH4EOOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 863353.

CONTENTS SLIDE

CS³ MESH⁴ EOOSC
Connecting European Data

END SLIDE

CS³ MESH⁴ EOOSC
Connecting European Data

Thank you!
Discover more on...

- cs3mesh4eosc.eu
- [company/cs3mesh4eosc](https://www.linkedin.com/company/cs3mesh4eosc)
- [@cs3mesh4eosc](https://twitter.com/cs3mesh4eosc)

CS3MESH4EOOSC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 863353.